

Values and Visions - European Policies and Strategies for the Cultural and Creative Industries after the Pandemic

Christos Carras

www.linkedin.com/in/christos-carras-16454a1a

Culture and the broader policy landscape

Well into the second year of pandemic disruption, there is broad agreement among policymakers and cultural professionals that a simple return to the *status quo ante* is not possible, nor even desirable, signalling a belief that there is much to be corrected and improved in the workings of the cultural sector. Digital production, and dissemination became the norm. Online cultural consumption provided much needed engagement and distraction from lockdown monotony, seeming to highlight its importance for wellbeing. 2020 was also a year in which the sector was often taken to task on critical political issues such as BLM, decolonisation, the climate crisis, and gender equality. Incomes and revenues dried up as live cultural experiences ground to a halt. Funders became more attuned to issues of impact in view of the multiple claims on resources. Covid 19 (C19) seemed to reveal a need to create new dynamics within the sector and adapt it to serve society today, generating the kind of values that are perceived to be important.

This paper examines certain core themes in broadly circulated recent reports and policy recommendations to understand how support for culture is being framed within the more general policy and funding environment in Europe whose priorities often predate the pandemic, as well as in responses to it. The EU had to devise significant ad hoc support instruments such as 'Support to mitigate Unemployment Risks in an Emergency' (SURE) and the Recovery and Resilience Fund and from this perspective, culture is seen as a contributor to economic development. On the other

hand, culture is also seen as an important facilitator of broader Commission policies, such as those related to social cohesion, the environment, and the smart economy. However, we must remember that culture is primarily the remit of member states and is therefore an area in which tensions at the heart of the European project appear. The paper focuses on the European Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) but the questions raised are more generally relevant.

What is fundamentally under discussion is how to understand, evaluate, and promote the value of culture in relation to broader political priorities. The risk, which I discuss in what follows, is that the policy frameworks or funding instruments might distort the understanding of cultural practices and their value to society. Going forward, the priorities that will be established will affect both programming and the way the sector engages with audiences and society more broadly: It is therefore crucial to think through the emerging trends with some critical clarity, to understand their political, social, and artistic implications. The latter, despite the central position of the arts in the cultural sector, often seem to be no more than an afterthought.

It is understandable that since “it is in the shared interest of all Member States to harness the full potential of education and culture as drivers for jobs, economic growth, social fairness, active citizenship as well as a means to experience European identity in all its diversity”¹ culture must be harmonised with overarching policies. Nonetheless, there are issues that I believe need to be reflected upon critically from the perspective of the cultural sector. It is also important to confront the temptation to make policy proposals for culture fit seamlessly into what one knows are already established overall policies at an EU level in order to maximise chances of gaining

¹ “A New European Agenda for Culture” 8

support. One should therefore take the time to reflect on whether the proposed policies and strategies are really optimal for the cultural sector (or for which parts of it) or whether they might perhaps achieve the objective of increased access to funds but at the cost of being squeezed into an overall policy framework with consequences that we should at least understand. Examples of such overriding frameworks which inflect culture in a variety of ways by defining overall economic, social, or environmental policies are the New Green Deal, the Digital Single Market Regulation, the Smart Specialisation Strategy, and more generally the actions ‘Shaping Europe’s Digital Future’, the New European Bauhaus as well as directives related to competition and the internal market, labour rights and discrimination. Because of the general recognition of the cultural sector’s importance, it is important to think deeply, and in as granular a fashion as possible about the pre-existing challenges that have become even more acute during the pandemic.

A heterogeneous sector

First, an introductory remark on the cultural sector itself. There are frequently discrepancies in what activities are captured in statistics and policies, making the precise comparison of data difficult.² Perhaps the most commonly used definition is by UNESCO³, but in view of the European focus of this paper, here is the ‘open-ended’ definition of the Cultural and Creative Sectors used in the proposal for a regulation establishing the Creative Europe programme (2021 to 2027): “The

² See Ernst and Young Consulting. 2021: 50 for example.

³ “Those sectors of organized activity that have as their main objective the production or reproduction, the promotion, distribution or commercialization of goods, services and activities of content derived from cultural, artistic or heritage origins.” see: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013R1295&from=EN#d1e527-221-1>, art. 2

sectors include architecture, archives, libraries and museums, artistic crafts, audio-visual (including film, television, video games and multimedia), tangible and intangible cultural heritage, design (including fashion design), festivals, music, literature, performing arts, books and publishing, radio, and visual arts.”⁴ This definition encompasses a highly heterogeneous range of activities: Imagine trying to devise policies for “the Movement Industries”, including everything from Super-tankers to e-scooters.⁵ This diversity is also reflected in the different effects of the pandemic on subsectors (for example the performing arts vs. gaming), in the varying levels of dependence on public or philanthropic support, and in the different kinds of value chains that make up each subsector. We should also consider how digitisation has impacted the sector: the large platforms (such as Facebook, YouTube or Instagram) are today primary interfaces between cultural production and consumption, creating new challenges for understanding both audiences and cultural organisations, the latter for over a year now having in effect become broadcasters. Finally, we need to think seriously about the role of amateur cultural production. Not only are the lines between professional and amateur often blurred with many arts organisations working with and presenting content by non-professionals, it may also be the case that vast areas of cultural activity, frequently within minority ethnic communities who are underrepresented in the programs of mainstream arts organisations, might be off the radar of most analysis that deals with professional cultural production, while being important for the cultural vibrancy of society as a whole. This heterogeneity must be kept in mind when discussing

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013R1295&from=EN#d1e527-221-1> Article 2., Definitions.

⁵ To be fair, there are specific policies for the audiovisual sector and also increasingly for music, but the overall point remains, I believe, valid.

policies for the sector.⁶

Which priorities for the CCIIs?

There is by now a good understanding of the financial impacts of the pandemic. The Ernst & Young (2021) study reports a 31% drop in revenues, equivalent to €199 billion, for the EU CCIIs in 2020 compared to 2019. This reduction is very unequally distributed between the subsectors however, with the performing arts and music hardest hit (-90% and -73% respectively) and radio the least (-20%) The video games industry reported a 9% gain. (EY, 2021: 6). The IDEA Consult study for the European Parliament provides an interesting analysis by subsector. (Voldere et al, 2021: 41-54)

Although this is taking time to be widely understood, there is every reason to fear that this situation will only improve slowly and over a longer period of time than one might have hoped. Some more vulnerable cultural organisations will cease operations and it is also likely that some cultural workers, whose precarity has been spotlighted during the pandemic, will have had to shift their careers in different directions.⁷ For those remaining and whose income is at least in part dependent on the collection of payments related to various forms of rights, the radical reduction in performances of the past many months will translate into a drop in revenues well into 2022. The backlog of productions will create bottlenecks that will lead to delays and cancellations of new work. Tourism, a major driver of several sub-sectors will not have returned to pre-pandemic levels before at least 2023. Moreover, some studies such as the one published by the IMF (Tahsin Saadi Sedik and Rui Xu, 2020) suggest

⁶ See also DISCE. 2020: 4-5

⁷ See "Ein Drittel der freien Musiker Berlins gibt den Beruf auf," for a German perspective on this issue.

that the overall economic recovery may be slower than expected, with inevitable consequences for the cultural sector.

It is therefore abundantly clear that the cultural sector will need more support than pre-C19, at many levels, in many forms, and for a considerable time. In Europe there have been many support programs, both nationally and at the level of the EU. A reasonably updated resource for tracking the former is the *Compendium of Cultural Policies and Trends*.⁸ The EU has increased support through various funding instruments, both transversal and sectoral.⁹ It is difficult to calculate the total support for culture through EU funding since it comes from a wide range of sources (e.g. Erasmus +, Horizon Europe, and a range of other frameworks that might provide opportunities for cultural organisations such as the New European Bauhaus, Digital Europe, various innovation programs and, going forward, the Recovery and Resilience Facility). Only Creative Europe is sector-specific and has a budget of €2.4 billion for 2021-2027. To put this in perspective, the total German Federal pandemic aid package for the cultural sector to date is worth €2 billion and French government support amounts to around €5 billion. These shortfalls are noted for example in the European Parliament resolution of 17 September 2020 on the cultural recovery of Europe¹⁰ which makes a comprehensive case for increased support for culture, one that has been echoed by a number of sectoral organisations as well, for example in the *Cultural Deal for Europe*.¹¹

In other words, there is a clear need for the cultural sector to fight for more

⁸ <https://www.culturalpolicies.net/covid-19/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/resources/coronavirus-response>

¹⁰ Cultural recovery of Europe - Thursday, 17 September 2020," n.d.

¹¹ "A Cultural Deal for Europe," n.d.

support, in competition with other sectors from health and education to travel and tourism. And, as Marc Lhermitte has noted "it is undeniable that other industries have been able to better explain their value and potential, and channel public support." (EY, 2021: 11) This context has reopened the discussion around culture's value to society and the economy as a whole and the structural and strategic changes that will make it more robust and resilient (to use two of the 'hot' adjectives of the moment) in the long term. There seems to be a broad consensus regarding some of these strategic and structural transformations. Despite nuances and variations there are three areas in particular which emerge from almost all of them that I propose to discuss: addressing the structural fragility of the sector's labour models; embracing, mastering, and deepening the digital transformation; establishing what one might call a 'new sectoral social contract'.¹² Table 1. presents some of the relevant conclusions and recommendations of five general and two sectoral recent reports.¹³

Fragility of the CCI's Labour Models

The overall precarity of the workforce in the cultural sector is by now well understood and documented. According to EU Labour Force Survey data, in 2019 32% of the cultural workforce was self-employed (vs. 14% in general) and 75% were in full-time employment (vs. 81% in general). Precarity is however also related to the more general characteristics of the sector:

"[...] artists and cultural workers have atypical work patterns. These include the non-standard nature of their working conditions, status and income, the un-

¹² Innovation, entrepreneurship, and new business models are also frequently mentioned, but their inclusion would excessively expand the scope of this paper.

¹³ The full references of the documents cited in this paper can be found at the end.

Table 1: Recommendations in recent reports that are relevant to the themes analysed in the paper.

Source	Labour Models	Digital Transformation	Cultural 'social contract'
OECD September 2020	- Measures to help the self-employed and small firms adapt to structural changes and seize new opportunities, including digital tools	- Invest in digital infrastructure that can amplify advances in cultural and creative sectors	Promote greater complementarities between culture and other policy sectors: - Education, particularly in the use of new digital tools that build on gaming technologies and new forms of cultural content - Health care and social services - to improve well-being, prevent illness or delay its onset, favour the adoption of healthy habits, and prevent social isolation, among others - Use targeted cultural policies to address social issues such as intercultural dialogue or the integration and valorisation of
IDEA Consult for the European Parliament February 2021	- Ensure sustainable CCS working conditions and invest in a fair work system with special focus on the most fragile parts. - Focus on lasting measures far beyond emergency support and understand the need for the establishment of legal social rights for cultural workers	- React quickly and with determination on the digital boost due to the pandemic in 2020 - ensure appropriate (legal) frameworks for CCS earning as well as broad digital access – both based on the values of democratic systems	- Invest in and make further use of the multidimensional potential of the CCS for societies and citizens in Europe, - raise awareness for social innovation
Ernst & Young report for GESAC January 2021	- Promote the EU's diversified cultural offering by ensuring a solid legal framework to allow for the development of private investment in production and distribution, providing the necessary conditions for an adequate return on investment for businesses and guaranteeing appropriate income for creators		- Use the CCIs – and the multiplied power of their millions of individual and collective talents – as a major accelerator of social, societal and environmental transitions in Europe.
UNESCO 2020		- adaptation of cultural policies and programmes to the digital age	
KEA report for the European Investment Fund * January 2021		- CCS content is increasingly consumed digitally through new access points and formats - Revenue generation is growing thanks to new digital products, services and business models - A revised EU regulatory framework contributes to the creation of a level playing field in the digital market and helps to unlock new revenue sources	- Environmental awareness and creative leadership drive greener business solutions and generate societal engagement - The CCS are spearheading new forms of work, with agile cooperation across smaller structures. New cooperative models help the CCS to address structural fragmentation and support cross-sectorial collaborations
NEMO January 2021		- Continued investment and support for general and sometimes basic development of digital skills and infrastructure of museums - Comprehensive digital transition should include addressing the development of sound metrics, frameworks and methods to	- open up and make use of museums' potential to serve as places where well-being is increased and mental health supported as well as public interaction is encouraged in a safe way and all forms of learning [are] stimulated
IETM February 2021	- respect the human values of all those participating in the ecosystem - practices based on economic practices which are sustainable over a longer period		- create the right conditions for artistic practices to also have a positive and demonstrable social impact - respect the broader ecologies the performing arts is part of

* This reports outlines trends that are actively shaping the CCS market in Europe, not strictly speaking recommendations

predictability of the end product of artistic work and of its reception, the fact that artistic creation is both time- and labour-intensive, business models driven by artistic excellence and other societal values rather than market goals, and propensity for cross-border mobility (which includes atypical situations that aren't easily translated into pre-existing categories associated with visas, social protection or taxation)." (Culture Action Europe and Dâmaso 2021: 7)

Furthermore, "the EU Labour Force Survey does not consider in its statistics the great number of 'invisible' workers in the CCS: temporary and intermittent workers, persons working under unpaid volunteer programmes and persons holding a second job in the cultural or creative field while maintaining a first main non-cultural occupation." (Voldere et al. 2021: 16) Finally, the shift to digital has further destabilised the sector by significantly modifying production and consumption modes and value chains.

Reports and policy recommendations underline the need for a profound understanding of the sector's conditions in order to adapt existing EU legislation and develop new ones that will address the primary concerns: fair income, rights enforcement, regulatory systems, access to information and education.¹⁴ To these I would also add the importance of structurally eradicating discrimination of all kinds within the sector's hierarchy and protecting artistic freedom, both of which are primarily the domain of national legislation. It will be interesting to see what dynamics emerge from the EU Social Summit being held in Porto at the time of writing these lines as member states push back against the desire of the Commission to regulate these areas more forcefully. There is an almost unanimous embrace of

¹⁴ See Culture Action Europe and Dâmaso 2021:36-40, and Voldere et al. 2021: 100-104

cultural work's more general contribution to the economy and society. If it is the case that the CCI's are (and are increasingly promoted and defended as) one of the most dynamic sectors of the European economy, with multiple direct and indirect benefits to society as a whole (on which more below) and function as a 'prototyping' lab in relation to technological and social innovation, then it is a serious issue that they rest on largely unsustainable labour relations and work conditions. Beyond this however, I would suggest that the case of the CCI's raises broader questions, with implications for the EU as a whole and even our conception of work.

A first line of questioning might focus on the mobility of workers in the cultural sector, a dimension that has been widely identified as being essential not only for facilitating creative processes but also for enhancing the sense of a shared European cultural area. The case of the CCI's then, combining the support for mobility and the necessary improvement of working conditions, would seem to be a test area for a profound harmonisation of regulations across member states. This is a need that was recognised in the 'European Parliament resolution of 17 September 2020 on the cultural recovery of Europe'¹⁵ and has been taken up by the sector itself.¹⁶

A second, more radical area for further research and experimentation might focus on what the CCI's may suggest regarding new, contemporary conceptions of work. It is not feasible to radically change the importance of self-employment and project-based work in general because it is in the DNA of how new cultural content is produced. It is also characteristic of many types of work in the platform economy, whose importance is growing. Likewise, whereas some sub-sectors have adaptable

¹⁵ (2020/2708(RSP)), resolution 11

¹⁶ See for example <https://cultureactioneurope.org/news/voices-of-culture-working-conditions-of-artists-and-cultural-workers/>

and robust business models, many are and will remain largely dependent on public, grassroots, or philanthropic support in various forms, whilst nonetheless providing services that are seen as beneficial, even essential. Moreover, the new value chains created through the digital transition raise serious issues regarding the remuneration of cultural work. Finally, as several reports have noted, there are large numbers of people who contribute in important ways to the vitality of the CCIs but do not register at all in sectoral statistics regarding employment, social security, and remuneration. It is not by accident that the onset of the pandemic saw a renewed interest in the idea of a universal basic income (UBI) or similar approaches to guaranteeing that there is a minimum revenue floor through which citizens cannot fall. The experience of widespread precarity, the renewed awareness of the importance of solidarity, perceived simplicity and ease of application and the simple fact that, to meet the needs of the poorer sections of their societies, many governments adopted policies of cash transfers brought this form of policy closer to home. Though the idea of a UBI has yet to become mainstream and entails many complex issues,¹⁷ the case of the CCIs during the pandemic could provide an opportunity to rethink the relationship between value, employment, and remuneration in ways that are important not only for the sector but for society as a whole.¹⁸

Embracing, Mastering, And Deepening Digital Transformation

In the words of a July 2020 report: "Digital adoption in Europe jumped from 81

¹⁷ See Parijs and Vanderborght. 2017 for an in-depth discussion and *Might the pandemic pave the way for a universal basic income?* and The Economist. 2021-03-02, accessed 2021-04-30, for example for a discussion in relation to the pandemic.

¹⁸ See Carras and Van Parijs, n.d.

percent to 95 percent as a result of the COVID-19 crisis—a rise that would have taken two to three years in most industries at pre-pandemic growth rates.” (McKinsey, 2020) Entertainment (not the same as but overlapping with the CCIs) was the sector that had the second largest number of first-time digital users, had the highest satisfaction scores and the second highest percentage of users declaring that they would continue using digital services after the pandemic. (ibid) Indeed, in the wake of the pandemic closures the reaction of most (if not all) CCI organisations was to increase their social media presence and enrich their digital offering. For some subsectors (e.g., digital gaming, music streaming, many archives) this was not a new situation, but for many, especially the performing arts, live music and, museum and heritage organisations the evolution was brutal and the realisation that this was not temporary incited much thought. Government support in most EU countries almost always included digital initiatives, something that accelerated the shift of productions to this area. There have been many interesting artistic projects and platforms, many making innovative and intelligent use of the formats offered by digital production and / or telematic performance.

However, as the year drew on various problems and limits of increased digitisation became increasingly apparent. The OECD ‘Culture Shock’ report underlines many of them, while retaining an optimistic tone:

“While the provision of free and digitally mediated cultural content is not sustainable over time, it has opened the door to many future innovations. To capitalise on them, there is a need to address the digital skills shortages within the sector and improve digital access beyond large metropolitan areas, with the additional consideration that digital access does not replace a live cultural experience or all the jobs that go with it.” (OECD, 2020: 3).

Many reports have stressed that digital sales have not and probably cannot replace physical sales (EY:34) and surveys indicate that the growth in online cultural consumption has not been matched by a tendency to purchase cultural goods online.¹⁹ The transformation of the value chain within the CCIs also creates new challenges for cultural workers and artists to receive fair remuneration. As the study commissioned by the European Parliament notes:

“Member States did not speed up to effectively implement the EU Copyright Directive nationally. IP support and help desks often lack sufficient CCI knowledge to provide adequate support services tailored to the needs of the CCIs. Furthermore, the use of algorithms is still extremely untransparent - especially on the major global digital platforms, which reduces further the earning potential of many CCS actors in Europe. Fair payment of digital cultural creation is far from being in place. Many EU CCS actors lack appropriate digital skills, while having no legal rights to access related training (due to their specific working conditions and/or contracts).” (Voldere et al. 2021: 67)

The lack of skill sets within organisations or their capacity to develop them is a significant problem and risks creating a new ‘digital divide’. The report by the Network of European Museum Organisations for example clearly indicated this risk: “Large museums with more than 100 employees show a low (9%) need of getting support for digital transition. Small and medium sized museums express about the same need (37% respectively 39%).” (NEMO, 2021: 18) As noted above, the digital transformation affects different sub-sectors very differently, and for those most

¹⁹ See for example the Digital Audience Survey by the Audience Agency (Audience Agency 2020) and the McKinsey report cited above.

dependent on physical delivery, apart from the issues related to revenues, the perceived risk is a flattening of the cultural landscape. As the IETM notes: “there are performances that will never appear on the Internet, due to their genre and nature, their way of interacting with audiences...” (Polivtseva, 2020: 5)

Over and above these important issues what has been to a large degree missing from the discussion are questions of how this increased digital activity engages the CCIs (especially the more public-facing arts organisations) in the broader media landscape. Arts organisations that have been broadcasting for over a year now and will continue doing so, are progressively becoming forms of media organisation. Using Yochai Benkler’s idea of a ‘hybrid media ecology’, Henry Jenkins and Mark Deuze had already noted in 2008 that within it

“commercial, amateur, governmental, non-profit, educational, activist and other players interact with each other in ever more complex ways. Each of these groups has the power to produce and distribute content and each of these groups is being transformed by their new power and responsibilities in this emerging media ecology.” (Jenkins and Deuze, 2008: 4)

Digital media challenge past conceptions of civic and political engagement and agency. As the Council of Europe ‘Online Participation in Culture and Politics: Towards More Democratic Societies?’ report notes: “In both cultural and political online spaces, the lines are blurring between consumer and producer, the roles of traditional gatekeepers and institutions have shifted, and new types of individual and collective forms of action have emerged.” (Council of Europe, 2018: 35).

Importantly, this ecology is also an ecology of audiences, something that CCIs should be particularly interested in. As Sonia Livingstone noted in 2013 “where once people moved in and out of their status as audiences, using media for specific

purposes and then doing something else [...] in our present age of continual immersion in media, we are now continually and unavoidably audiences at the same time as being consumers, relatives, workers, and [...] citizens and publics.” (Livingstone, 2013: 22) Within this evolving ecology, it could be argued that public-facing cultural organisations now sit at a nodal point, connecting cultural production and consumption, intervening in social and political debates, providing both information and entertainment, driving community formation and being sources of community support, and facilitating the flow of ideas from one field to another (e.g., from art to scientific research and education, or vice versa). They occupy this position both as media organisations (broadcasting organisations with strong connections to subscribers, supporters, friends, cultural consumers) and as what might resemble cultural intermediaries, bringing together the different knowledge bases and aspirations of artists, curators, researchers, policymakers, cultural technicians, communities, and consumers. In this process, although digital technologies have played a significant enabling role, it is essential not to forget that we are primarily talking about a cultural phenomenon: a shift in the directionality of media production and consumption, a disintegration of traditional centres of informational authority, and the emergence of new modes of constitution publics and counterpublics.

To my mind, this is perhaps the most significant dynamic of what we call the digital transition (a terms that privileges the technological dimension). Although it has led to unprecedented concentration of power, it has also opened the possibility for organisations that have accumulated social and cultural capital – and arts organisations are certainly such – to be active in new ways in this highly complex public sphere. This is a vast area of research and I touch upon it here only to suggest that the understanding of this digital public sphere and the position of CCI within

the media ecology that so profoundly structures it, requires a broad range of knowledge and expertise including research into audiences and media, by cultural practitioners, civil society representatives, academics, and policy experts. It also requires cultural professionals to be trained not only in using digital tools and platforms, but in understanding their role in the media landscape and how it affects their constituencies, artists, and audiences for example. In other words, the digital transition requires that we go much further than new production, dissemination, rights management, and monetisation models. As the Council of Europe Report mentioned above underlines, the hopes and expectations for the new digital environment reveal opportunities and challenges in equal measure. (Ibid: 37-38) These aspects are all the more important if, as it is assumed in most policy proposals, culture has a central role to play as a diffuser of values such as diversity, equity, sustainability and innovation. Which brings me to the third area I would like to discuss.

A new sectoral social contract

As I write these lines (in early May 2021) the Portuguese Presidency of the Council of the EU is organising a Conference on the topic of “Culture, Cohesion and Social Impact”.²⁰ The titles of the panel sessions almost perfectly sum up the primary areas in which it is proposed that the CCI should engage even more deeply and systematically: Culture, Mental health and Well-being; Culture, Cohesion and Territory; Culture and Environmental Sustainability; Culture and Gender Equality; Agenda 2030 and Sustainable Development Goals. I would add “Culture and Innovation”, “Culture and Education”, and would enrich “gender equality” with “racial

²⁰ <http://ppue.gepac.gov.pt/conferencias-en?name=Conference%20Culture%20Cohesion%20e%20Social%20Impact>

equality” and combatting ableism to complete the picture. Many of these are long-standing priorities and many cultural organisations have of course been active in these fields for some years. The *New European Agenda for Culture (2018)*²¹ already mentions education, social cohesion, wellbeing, sustainability, and innovation for example. The idea that successful policies should be measured not only in terms of GDP, GVA or employment but also ‘wellbeing’ is by now well entrenched and has been monitored using a range of mechanisms such as the Eurostat Quality of Life Scoreboard, OECD Wellbeing Research, the United Nations Human Development Index, or other approaches such as the Boston Consulting Group’s ‘Sustainable Economic Development Assessment’. However, it is interesting and significant to note that ‘culture’ does not figure as an independent dimension in any of these methodologies²². Nor indeed is ‘culture’ one of the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals which are emerging as a universally accepted policy framework for sustainability, an absence that has not been lost on the cultural sector.²³

This seems to me to create a paradoxical situation. On the one hand, culture is not a fundamental dimension in assessing wellbeing or one of the SDGs, on the other cultural policies and policy proposals affirm its connection to all six political priorities of the EU in the current period,²⁴ and emphasise its role in promoting social wellbeing. Cultural organisations have also put their voices behind this role. For example, the manifesto *A Cultural Deal for Europe* begins by affirming that “Culture is what brings us together. It is at the basis of the European project and a catalyst for

²¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/document/new-european-agenda-culture-swd2018-267-final>

²² It is a sub-component of ‘Leisure and social interactions’ in the Eurostat report.

²³ <https://cultureactioneurope.org/files/2019/09/Implementing-Culture-in-Sustainable-Development-Goals-SDGs.pdf>

²⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/policies/strategic-framework-eus-cultural-policy>

the future of Europe. Culture carries tremendous intrinsic value and contributes significantly to the economy. Culture has always been a “social glue” and vibrant resource, able to heal wounds in times of crisis.”²⁵ However, one needs to understand what this healing entails, perhaps challenge some of the assumptions on which the claim is based and finally also ask what might be side-lined in this meshing of cultural practice with ‘the real world’.

2020 was a year in which the cultural sector was often directly challenged by society on various fronts: the environment, Black Lives Matter, the restitution of colonial era artefacts, gender equality for example, as well as its own labour relations. Moreover, with the need for solidarity that the pandemic created, many cultural professionals re-evaluated the significance of their engagement with the communities that are organically related to them in comparison to the role of their institutions as place-makers for example. The search for an understanding of the relationship between the ‘art world’ and the ‘real world’ has a long and fascinating history.²⁶ For example, the historical avant-garde, driven by the life-shattering experience of the WW1 trenches, strived for the elimination of the gap between art and life because it wanted to destroy the symbolic and conceptual order that sustained a world of injustice and destruction: life should become more like art, with its capacity for radical imagination, a desire that underpinned much of the politics of May ‘68 also. Likewise, there is a rich history of institutional critique which attempts to reveal how the art world can function as a distracting front-end for the extractive

²⁵ <https://cultureactioneurope.org/knowledge/a-cultural-deal-for-europe/#:~:text=There%20is%20no%20recovery%20or,heart%20of%20the%20Europe an%20project.>

²⁶ Though we should of course not forget that the ‘real’ world is also symbolically constituted.

and exploitative back-end of capitalism,²⁷ and many fascinating examples of artistic or curatorial work that attempts to rectify social inequalities that permeate the art world itself.²⁸ Recently, Peter Weibel has written about the connection between political activism and artistic practice in terms of the “parallel between performative, interactive and participative art forms and global activism” (Weibel, 2015: 25) and concludes that “it is only performances in the public sphere of the street, anonymously and without institutional invitation, that are cultivated in activism: with the objective of solving social rather than artistic problems.” (ibid: 60) So, in view of the importance of culture for social cohesion and wellbeing,²⁹ is the European Commission militating for ‘artivism’ to be the guiding principle of cultural work? Maybe not. A ‘New European Cabaret Voltaire’ would not get very far, but the *New European Bauhaus*³⁰ might well. If these matters seem far removed from issues of policymaking, they are in fact not and I would like to touch upon two issues that illustrate the complexity of the ‘new social contract’ of culture.

Two meanings of ‘culture’ and their implications

The first is the need for conceptual clarity and analytical granularity. Raymond Williams, when discussing the origins and use of the word ‘culture’ identifies three meanings, two of which are once again important at this crucial moment for the cultural sector: culture as a “particular way of life” and culture as “the works and practices of intellectual and especially artistic activity.” (Williams, 1985: 90). He concludes: “These variations, of whatever kind, necessarily involve alternative views

²⁷ See for example (Fraser, 2005)

²⁸ See for example (Reilly, 2018)

²⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/policies/selected-themes/cohesion-and-well-being>

³⁰ https://europa.eu/new-european-bauhaus/about/about-initiative_en

of the activities, relationships and processes which this complex word indicates. The complexity, that is to say, is not finally in the word but in the problems which its variations of use significantly indicate." (ibid: 92) Culture may indeed in the first sense be a "social glue" and this conception may underlie political priorities such as the much-debated *European Way of Life*,³¹ but glue, when used well, is invisible. Being specific about cultural activities is the only way to ensure that this cross-cutting dimension does not result in the disappearance of the sector. For the purposes of devising a cultural politics, something like Williams' second definition is what we need to have in mind, in a form that is relevant to today's context. This is why I have underlined the need for a much higher degree of granularity in our approach to the cultural sector, but also for a more inclusive understanding of the elements that make it up. Furthermore, as the authors of the excellent 2016 report 'Understanding the value of arts & culture' write that:

"...we need a 'multi-modal' understanding of arts participation. Attendance in various places outside the home, personal creation and performance in private and public spaces, and increasing participation through electronic media [...]" and also that "The evolving ecology of commercial, amateur, interactive and subsidised engagement needs to be better understood, and seen as enriching rather than antagonistic." (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016: 29)

For it to be useful at the level of policymaking, this fine-grained approach should drive a radical review of data-collection methodologies in Europe, bringing our understanding of the cultural field up to date, and ideally include both qualitative and quantitative research on a regular and systematic basis. It should also be noted

³¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life_en

that our understanding of the cultural sector is heavily influenced by in-depth analysis conducted in a small number of (wealthier) EU member states. In devising an EU policy, it would be essential to have extensive research of this new kind across the Union. Culture is indeed a complex ecosystem, and its various constituent parts need bespoke attention to thrive.

Cross-cutting Culture

Leading on from this, secondly, we should remember that 'culture' in the first sense identified by Williams is fundamentally a descriptive term, whereas 'culture' in the second sense is called upon to actively have effects on ways of life in accordance with political goals. We must therefore ask exactly what kinds of cultural practices and approaches, and which sectors help achieve broader social policies, and what kind of efficacy is this? Some political priorities are perhaps relatively easy to understand, such as supporting the drive to emissions neutrality in Europe in line with the *European Green Deal*.³² Here the CCIs can concretely work at neutralising the environmental impact of their production and dissemination models. This is already gaining momentum in many sub-sectors such as the performing arts, the visual arts, and the fashion industry, though there is still a way to go.³³ But how does one harmonise all European states at this level, bearing in mind that European financing for cultural production is a small fraction of the total budget and that national cultural initiatives are defined locally? The European Climate Law³⁴ engages member states to take the necessary measures to achieve climate-neutrality but

³² https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

³³ Although absolutely essential, carbon neutrality creates significant challenges for the sector, for example at the level of mobility which as we have seen is important.

³⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020PC0080&from=EN>

obliging them all to make climate action by their cultural sectors a precondition for financial or other support would take a much more intrusive use of the competencies afforded by the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union.

Another interesting example concerns the cross-sectoral collaboration of arts and scientific or technological research. There are many noteworthy initiatives in this field (disclaimer: I participate in some of them). That there is potential for powerful artwork to be produced through such collaboration has been clear for several decades from the programs of organisations such as Ars Electronica.³⁵ Along with other funding mechanisms a European program, STARTS,³⁶ provides financing for projects in this field, something that has no doubt driven its recent development. However, we are still far from understanding both the methodologies of art-science collaborations and the real contribution of art to science, beyond prototyping, testing and communicating. The flow in the other direction is much clearer as artists for decades now have been engaging with technologies, materials, and data in producing works that incorporate scientific understanding of the world. Nonetheless, one would not frame science as being worthy of support because it stimulates artists. Perhaps this example of art-science collaboration suggests the danger of confusing means and ends.

Culture and Wellbeing

When it comes to the contribution of the CCIs to social cohesion or wellbeing we enter the heart of a complicated issue, one in which the slipping back and forth between two meanings of 'culture' is a constant danger. In the first sense, the right of

³⁵ <https://ars.electronica.art/news/en/>

³⁶ <https://www.starts.eu/>

individuals to participate in and contribute to 'culture' is well established, going back to the 1966 UN International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (art. 15.1.a).³⁷ Subsequent conventions, such as the 2005 UN 'Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions' not only develop the idea of diversity but also qualify culture as being "essential for inclusive economic growth, reducing inequalities and achieving the goals set out in the 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda."³⁸ Here we already in the territory of the second meaning of 'culture' as well, that of specific activities that produce cultural goods and services.

In what way does culture promote overall social cohesion or wellbeing and not that of particular communities? To what degree is cohesion itself an operative term in today's incredibly multi-layered and intersectional understanding of identities, of which cultural productions are one subset of elements? What really matters, I believe, is the robust protection by law and in practice of peoples' right to produce, participate in and consume whatever they want. The recognition and implementation of this right is a bedrock of social cohesion in general. Cultural artefacts tend to be operative elements in the cohesion of specific communities, audiences, and publics and these often have antagonistic relationships both among themselves and with more generally hegemonic instances of power.

In a similar vein I would argue that the evidence of the effects of art in education are not to be sought in metrics such as higher performance, but in the exposure of young people to alternative imaginaries and to forms of creativity that reveal their own capacity to imagine: an artwork can be a means to an enriched

³⁷ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cescr.aspx>

³⁸ <https://en.unesco.org/creativity/convention>

educational experience, but an enriched educational experience is not the end of the artwork. The relation of art to health and mental wellbeing, around which by all accounts further and more refined research is needed, is another important and similar question. Beyond the obvious fact that engaging with art one appreciates is a source of joy, there are indeed many examples of artistic practices being mobilised within the medical or paramedical field, both by artists and medical professionals. In both these cases, the desired ends are education or health. Cultural practice can clearly be a means to enhance these ends, but policies should to my mind focus on promoting the engagement of education and health with the CCIs, incentivising the adoption of creative tools and approaches by these fields rather than on instrumentalising culture. This would achieve the desired cross-sectoral synergies and would also create employment opportunities without misrepresenting the objectives of cultural and creative practitioners in a generalised fashion.

Means and Ends

These are of course massively complicated and fascinating issues that I cannot do justice to here. My concern is that we should not confuse the role of art and creative practices in a range of individual and broader social outcomes with the reasons for their support. When funding is involved, this confusion can have real consequences on the decisions artists and creatives make. I quote from the handbook produced by an important European cultural organization to assist its members in evaluating the effects on wellbeing of their projects:

“...representatives of cultural organisations have complained that they often feel unequal to the task of justifying to their funders their costs, their activities or their very existence, in terms of quantifiable economic or social returns to investments. Clear enough [sic], most of those requests show little, if any,

appreciation of art "for art's sake".³⁹

But "art for art's sake" has already been deconstructed in practice from within the arts world. The very expression sets up an opposition between a 'useless', 'elitist' pursuit and 'real' social value. If for decades already artists had not been curious about using scientific data or testing new materials, if disabled dancers had not wanted to create amazing choreographies, if theatre directors had not felt the need to work against the politics of representation and promote works with marginalized communities, if curators hadn't thought deep and hard about decolonisation, we wouldn't even be having this discussion now. In other words, the role of the CCIs is to constantly create and experiment, inevitably from within the tensions and dynamics of their world. To make this point clearer: the force of cultural and creative practices is not primarily that they resolve critical issues. Rather, this work can identify and express problems, injustices and aspirations, give them form and mobilise the political imaginary even before these issues are broadly recognised or formulated as political priorities. Creatives do this as engaged artists, not as social workers or policy makers. What are required are freedom of expression, access to information and education and material conditions that enable this work.

Their role cannot be to right the wrongs of the world. Which is not the same thing as saying that creative work cannot create circumstances of understanding or even mobilization of communities and individuals that do combat injustice. Nor that the experience of art is not a factor in wellbeing. But it is interesting to study the "Sustainable Economic Development Assessment" developed by the Boston

³⁹ I cannot help but remember Ronald Reagan's 1967 chastisement of "subsidized curiosity" in pushing for the 'reform' of the US University system.

Consulting Group.⁴⁰ Using this composite metric, wellbeing is assessed as a function of income levels, stability, and employment, the key public investment areas of education, health, and infrastructure and access to these, social aspects (equality, governance, and civil society) and the environment. In other words, wellbeing is enhanced (when it is) through a hard core of political priorities not principally through participation in culture. No doubt it would be convenient if culture could alleviate these problems, obviating the need to shake up the politics of the market or improve governance, but this cannot be done.

Imagining a radical democracy

So, should the CCIs be expected to “help form brave and bold public solutions that are grounded in long-term perspectives of environmental sustainability and social resilience.”? (Macfarland, Agace & Hayes, 2020: 13) A cultural politics should frame the environment in which the CCIs function, but at the level of politics, not content. For example: engaging the CCIs in policies related to climate-neutrality; ensuring that forms of structural discrimination on basis of gender, sexual preference, race, or disability are eliminated within the industry; developing and promoting new labour relations or social protection nets. These could all be factors in funding without determining what the CCIs are for. Likewise, it is good that we have moved away from economic spill-over to include other forms of value. The danger is in trying to incorporate these forms into the old evaluation mentality. There is a need to develop new frameworks that reflect the current ecology of cultural creation, participation, and consumption, but primarily geared to deeper understanding and qualitative evaluation. As the authors of the AHRC report

⁴⁰ <https://www.bcg.com/en-gr/publications/2019/seda-measuring-well-being>

mentioned above note:

“Accounting for human experiences of art and culture calls for multi-criteria analyses and a range of approaches, in order to span the depth and the breadth of research. Such evaluation is often not suited to accountability, which often needs headline results, single measures, and weighted aggregates. This is why it is important that evaluation should not be thought of as being primarily undertaken for the purposes of accountability or advocacy.” (Crossick and Kaszynska, 2016: 10)⁴¹

Furthermore, the process of defining cultural value needs to be much more inclusive itself. As Eleonor Belfiore asks:

“...whose ideas of ‘cultural value’ drive decisions over investment and funding justified in terms of public benefits? And can the process through which cultural authority is exercised in this decision-making process be made genuinely democratic and accountable? What is the responsibility of public policy towards those who appear as ‘losers’ in these struggles over validation of their cultural value?” (Belfiore, 2020: 394)

The idea of ‘art for art’s sake’ has already been reworked by a significant portion of the artworld itself, as a result of broader political dynamics to which artists are often particularly attuned. On the other hand, the oft-brandished accusation of elitism can be extremely dangerous: a cynical repression of critical thought disguised as a heartfelt concern for democratic accessibility. Clearly, no creative

⁴¹ see also Goethe Institut, 2016: 6-7

work is good in virtue of being esoteric, but original ideas and practices that reframe our understanding of the world are, by definition, not widely shared. If by stressing the importance of wellbeing we intend more than simply being happy with what we have or doing well against the odds that have been stacked against us and on the contrary affirm that wellbeing will emerge from a fight against inequality and injustice, then we have first of all to identify these in all their forms and cultivate a radical imagination that enables us to see beyond what appears as second nature. Policies will focus on culture as an element of development or as a factor in wellbeing, but creative work, within a political framework that guarantees democratic access, is worth supporting on its own terms.

References

- 'A Cultural Deal for Europe'. n.d. Culture Action Europe. Accessed 8 May 2021. <https://cultureactioneurope.org/knowledge/a-cultural-deal-for-europe/>.
- 'A European Green Deal'. n.d. Text. European Commission - European Commission. Accessed 8 May 2021. https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en.
- 'A New European Agenda for Culture - SWD(2018) 267 Final | Culture and Creativity'. n.d. Accessed 8 May 2021. <https://ec.europa.eu/culture/document/new-european-agenda-culture-swd2018-267-final>.
- Belfiore, Eleonora. 2020. 'Whose Cultural Value? Representation, Power and Creative Industries'. *International Journal of Cultural Policy* 26 (3): 383-97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2018.1495713>.
- Boston Consulting Group. 2020. 'Measure Well-Being to Improve It'. Greece - EN. 22 July 2020. <https://www.bcg.com/en-gr/publications/2019/seda-measuring-well-being>.
- Carras, C. & Van Parijs, P. (n.d.) The European cultural sector, pandemic precarity, and Universal Basic Income [online]. Available from: <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/can-europe-make-it/european-cultural->

- sector-pandemic-precarity-and-universal-basic-income/ (Accessed 29 August 2021).
- 'The Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions'. 2018. Diversity of Cultural Expressions. 15 February 2018. <https://en.unesco.org/creativity/convention>.
- Council of Europe, 2018, 'Online Participation In Culture And Politics: Towards More Democratic Societies?', <https://rm.coe.int/second-thematic-report-based-on-the-indicator-framework-on-culture-and/16808d2514> (accessed 8 May 2021).
- Culture Action Europe & Dâmaso, M. 2021, Research for CULT Committee - 'The situation of artists and cultural workers and the post-COVID-19 Cultural Recovery in the European Union', European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, Brussels
- Culture Action Europe, n.d., 'Implementing Culture Within the Sustainable Development Goals', <https://cultureactioneurope.org/files/2019/09/Implementing-Culture-in-Sustainable-Development-Goals-SDGs.pdf> (accessed 5.8.21).
- Crossick, Geoffrey and Kaszynska, Patrycja. 2016, *Understanding the value of arts & culture*, Arts and Humanities Research Council, (UK)
- 'Cultural Recovery of Europe - Thursday, 17 September 2020'. n.d. Accessed 8 May 2021. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2020-0239_EN.html.
- 'Culture Shock: COVID-19 and the Cultural and Creative Sectors'. n.d. OECD. Accessed 21 March 2021. <http://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/culture-shock-covid-19-and-the-cultural-and-creative-sectors-08da9e0e/>.
- 'Digital Audience Survey | Findings'. 2020. The Audience Agency. 2020. <https://www.theaudienceagency.org/bounce-forwards/digital-audience-survey-findings>.
- DISCE. 2020, 'Managing Creative Economies as Cultural Ecosystems', <https://disce.eu/publications/> (accessed 8 May 2021).
- The Economist. 2021. 'Might the Pandemic Pave the Way for a Universal Basic Income?', 2 March 2021. <https://www.economist.com/finance-and-economics/2021/03/02/might-the-pandemic-pave-the-way-for-a-universal-basic-income>.

- 'Ein Drittel der freien Musiker Berlins gibt den Beruf auf'. n.d. Accessed 14 May 2021. <https://m.tagesspiegel.de/berlin/fragile-lebentwuerfe-nicht-nur-in-coronazeiten-ein-drittel-der-freien-musiker-berlins-gibt-den-beruf-auf/26853982.html>.
- Ernst & Young Consulting. 2021. *Rebuilding Europe - The cultural and creative economy before and after the COVID-19 crisis*.
- 'Europe's Migration to Digital Services during COVID-19 | McKinsey'. n.d. Accessed 8 May 2021. <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/europes-digital-migration-during-covid-19-getting-past-the-broad-trends-and-averages>.
- Fraser, Andrea. 2005. 'From the Critique of Institutions to an Institution of Critique'. September 2005. <https://www.artforum.com/print/200507/from-the-critique-of-institutions-to-an-institution-of-critique-9407>.
- Goethe Institut. 2016. 'Culture Works'. <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf94/culture-works-brochure-september-2016.pdf> (accessed 5.8.21).
- Jenkins, Henry, and Mark Deuze. 2008. 'Editorial: Convergence Culture'. *Convergence* 14 (1): 5-12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354856507084415>.
- Livingstone, Sonia. 2013. 'The Participation Paradigm in Audience Research'. *The Communication Review* 16 (1-2): 21-30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2013.757174>.
- Macfarland, C., Agace, M., & Hayes, C. 2020. *Creativity, Culture and Connection, Common Vision*, London, http://covi.org.uk/dev4/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Creativity-Culture-and-Connection_Common-Vision-report_September-2020.pdf
- NEMO-The Network of European Museum. n.d. 'NEMO Follow-up Report on the Continued Impact of Covid-19 on the Museum Sector'. NEMO - The Network of European Museum Organisations. Accessed 8 May 2021. <https://www.nemo.org/news/article/nemo/nemo-follow-up-report-on-the-continued-impact-of-covid-19-on-the-museum-sector.html>.
- New European Bauhaus, About the initiative [WWW Document], n.d. URL https://europa.eu/new-european-bauhaus/about/about-initiative_en (accessed 8 May 2021).

- 'New "Market Analysis of the Cultural and Creative Sectors in Europe"'. 2021. KEA. 10 February 2021. <https://keanet.eu/new-market-analysis-of-the-cultural-and-creative-sectors-in-europe/>.
- 'OHCHR | International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights'. n.d. Accessed 8 May 2021. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cescr.aspx>.
- Parijs, Philippe van, and Yannick Vanderborght. 2017. *Basic Income: A Radical Proposal for a Free Society and a Sane Economy*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Polivtseva, Elena. 2020. 'Live Arts in the Virtualising World'. IETM. 5 May 2020. <https://www.ietm.org/en/publications/live-arts-in-the-virtualising-world>.
- 'Promoting Our European Way of Life'. n.d. Text. European Commission - European Commission. Accessed 8 May 2021. https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/promoting-our-european-way-life_en.
- 'Regulation (Eu) No 1295/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Establishing the Creative Europe Programme (2014 to 2020) Of'. 2013. 11 December 2013. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32013R1295&from=EN#d1e496-221-1>.
- Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Establishing the Framework for Achieving Climate Neutrality and Amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 (European Climate Law), 2020, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020PC0080&from=EN> (accessed 8 May 2021).
- Reilly, Maura. 2018. *Curatorial Activism: Towards an Ethics of Curating*. New York: Thames & Hudson.
- Tahsin Saadi Sedik and Rui Xu. 2020. *A Vicious Cycle: How Pandemics Lead to Economic Despair and Social Unrest*. International Monetary Fund. <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2020/10/16/A-Vicious-Cycle-How-Pandemics-Lead-to-Economic-Despair-and-Social-Unrest-49806>.
- Voldere, Isabelle de, Martina Fraioli, Antonia Blau, Sina Lebert, Sylvia Amann, Joost Heinsius, European Parliament, et al. 2021. *Research for CULT Committee - Cultural and Creative Sectors in Post-COVID-19 Europe: Crisis Effects and Policy Recommendations*.

https://op.europa.eu/publication/manifestation_identifier/PUB_QA0121047E
NN.

Weibel, Peter, ed. 2015. *Global Activism: Art and Conflict in the 21st Century*. A ZKM Book. Karlsruhe: ZKM, Center for Art and Media Karlsruhe.

Williams, Raymond. 1985. *Keywords: A Vocabulary of Culture and Society*. Rev. ed. New York: Oxford University Press.

'Working Conditions of Artists & Cultural Workers'. n.d. Culture Action Europe. Accessed 8 May 2021. <https://cultureactioneurope.org/news/voices-of-culture-working-conditions-of-artists-and-cultural-workers/>.